

Corrosion inhibition of mild steel by ethyltriphenylphosphoniumiodide in acid medium

A. Goswami and V. K. Sharma*

Department of Chemistry, Shyam Lal College (University of Delhi), G. T. Road, Shahdara, Delhi-110 032, India

E-mail : drvinodsharma57@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Ethyltriphenylphosphoniumiodide (ETPPI) inhibitor was synthesised and its corrosion inhibiting behaviour for mild steel in H_2SO_4 (10^{-3} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-7} M) was studied at four different temperatures (298, 308, 318, 328 K). The optimum concentration of this compound for maximum inhibition efficiency was determined by galvanostatic method. ETPPI gave more than 95% inhibition in presence of 10^{-3} M H_2SO_4 at 298 K. Potentiodynamic polarization studies revealed that ETPPI is mixed inhibitor and good passivator in 1 N H_2SO_4 . According to temperature kinetics ETPPI obeyed Temkin's adsorption isotherm. Due to adsorption on metal surface. Certain quantum chemical parameters have been calculated to reinforce the electrochemical result.

Keywords : Corrosion, inhibition efficiency, mild steel.

Introduction

The growing need of metal in every walk of life, loss of it by corrosion has put a big question mark before the mankind. Regarding how to prevent it from being corroded so that it can be used to its maximum extent if not stopped completely. Generally the aim of investigation is to detect inhibitor, to determine the effect of inhibition, to investigate the mode of inhibition. The objective of the present investigation has been to study the mechanism of adsorption of ethyltriphenylphosphoniumiodide (ETPPI) which act as corrosion inhibitor in acidic solution¹⁻⁴. This present study describe the role of ethyltriphenylphosphoniumiodide^{5,6} as an inhibitor during anodic dissolution of mild steel and cathodic reduction of oxygen. The primary data have been collected on various of aspects of corrosion of mild steel in sulphuric acid in the presence of ETPPI. The result is supplemented with temperature kinetics^{7,8}, infrared studies⁹, scanning electron microscopy¹⁰ and quantum chemical studies^{11,12}.

Results and discussion

Galvanostatic polarisation studies :

Galvanostatic polarisation studies of mild steel were carried out in 1 N H_2SO_4 at four different temperatures 298, 308, 318 and 328 K give the cathodic and anodic polarization curves. Logarithms of current densities was

plotted against the corresponding electrode potential. Tafel slopes for cathodic and anodic process were calculated from which the nature and mechanism of hydrogen evolution and anodic metal dissolution reaction can be established. Corrosion parameters for mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Corrosion parameters of mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 in the presence of ETPPI by galvanostatic studies

Temp. (K)	Conc. (mol^{-1})	$-E_{corr}$ (mV)	b_c (mV/dec)	I_{Corr} (mA/cm^2)	I (%)
298	10^{-3}	490	185	0.22	95
	10^{-5}	495	130	0.81	81
	10^{-7}	475	90	1.3	72
	H_2SO_4	470	140	4.6	-
308	10^{-3}	495	140	0.33	93
	10^{-5}	498	180	1.2	76
	10^{-7}	470	80	1.5	70
	H_2SO_4	465	105	5.1	-
318	10^{-3}	500	250	1.4	84
	10^{-5}	502	75	4.1	55
	10^{-7}	450	80	6.0	33
	H_2SO_4	455	45	9.0	-
328	10^{-3}	510	255	3.5	70
	10^{-5}	491	65	5.2	56
	10^{-7}	452	70	7.0	41
	H_2SO_4	450	255	12.0	-

As the temperature increases the corrosion current value also increases which indicates that the extent of corrosion increases with increase in temperature. The cathodic and anodic Tafel slope's value in uninhibited solution remained constant with increase in temperature.

Galvanostatic studies in presence of ethyltriphenylphosphoniumiodide (ETPPI) :

1 N sulphuric acid containing various concentration of ETPPI was used for polarization studies at 298, 308, 318 and 328 K. According to graph plotted between the polarizing potential and logarithm of current densities, give the following result which is mentioned in Table 1. The following information regarding inhibitor can be received by Tafel slopes. ETPPI has shown no appreciable shift in open circuit potential (OCP) towards any direction at the same time (Table 1). It can be clearly seen that there is no appreciable change in E_{corr} value which makes this compound mixed type inhibitor. There is decrease in corrosion current I_{corr} value at lower temperature (298 K) as compared to the change in corrosion current value at higher temperature (328 K) as the concentration changed from 10^{-7} to 10^{-3} M is less. The more is the corrosion current value, the more will be the corrosion. That is why ETPPI belongs to Putilova's first class of inhibitor. According to Putilova's, the inhibitors which retards corrosion at ordinary temperature but enhanced corrosion at higher temperature, belongs to first class of inhibitors. The variations in Tafel slopes in irregular manner, shows that the reduction in I_{corr} value by increasing temperature and decreasing inhibitor concentration is being caused not only by the adsorption of the inhibitor on the surface alone but some other mechanism also involved. From the polarization data it can be seen that inhibitor act by both ways i.e. (i) blocking the active site for cathodic reaction. During cathodic polarization both molecular and protonated species will get adsorbed on the metal surface to block the active site with I^- providing active synergistic effect to this process of inhibition. ETPPI therefore, in acidic media undergoes small protonation reaction and form protonated species as per reaction given below.

(ii) During anodic polarization the adsorption takes places between the positive metal ion and the delocalized additive system, because of which the metal dissolution retards. From the structure it is clear that the π electron

system of the inhibitor molecule overlap with the vacant d orbital at surface of Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} resulting in a strong $d\pi$ - $p\pi$ interaction which is further assisted by the synergistic effect of I^- . As the anodic current value increases during the anodic dissolution process of metal, the surface metal atom combined with hydroxide, I^- ion and other ion present in the solution the adsorbed metal hydroxide $(\text{M-OH})_{\text{ads}}$ which further react with additive form of adduct of the type $(\text{M-In})_{\text{ads}}$ or type $(\text{M-OH-In})_{\text{ads}}/(\text{M-In-I})_{\text{ads}}/(\text{M-In-OH-I})_{\text{ads}}/(\text{M-In-I-OH})_{\text{ads}}/(\text{M-I-OH-In})_{\text{ads}}$ etc. Which cover the anodic site to reduce the extent of corrosion. At lower concentration and higher temperature, the adsorption tends to be weaker and time gap between adsorption and desorption becomes shorter, leading to greater exposure of bare surface, resulting in lower inhibition.

Thermodynamic and adsorption studies on acid corrosion of mild steel in the presence of ETPPI :

Since the corrosion rates are directly related to corrosion current, the inhibitor efficiencies I% for different concentrations of ETPPI at 298, 308, 318 and 328 K were calculated and tabulated in Table 3. It can be seen from graph that at 298 K the inhibition efficiency increases with increase in concentration, but the decrease with concentration is very less, whereas at higher temperature this decreases sharply. The plot of $\log \theta/1 - \theta$ vs $\log c$ shows that ETPPI at higher temperature follows Langmuir's adsorption isotherm because the time lag between adsorption and desorption becomes shorter and therefore, at any point of time it appears to be monomolecular. At lower temperature there is no general agreement with Langmuir's adsorption isotherm. This is primarily due to nonlinearity of the molecule, irregular protonation and intermolecular repulsion. But a general trend, that surface coverage decreases with increase in temperature, is very much obvious. Although Langmuir's general adsorption theory is inadequate to explain his tendency to adsorb in a multilayer manner. The data for ETPPI fits better in Temkin's adsorption isotherm in which, surface coverage (θ) shows a linear relationship with concentration. In order to calculate an approximate heat of adsorption Q of ETPPI over metal surface in 1 N sulfuric acid, with the help of graph drawn between $\log \theta/1 - \theta$ vs $1/T$, the value of Q are calculated from the straight line portion of the curve for 10^{-3} , 10^{-7} M inhibitor reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Calculated values of Q and E_{eff} for the corrosion of mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 in the presence of ETPPI

Concentration (mol L ⁻¹)	$-Q$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-E_{\text{eff}}$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)
10 ⁻³	28.70	27.60
10 ⁻⁵	20.80	25.30
10 ⁻⁷	23.20	24.84
H_2SO_4	-	13.80

The value of Q obtained, support the chemisorption and that is the reason the corrosion inhibition efficiency is more than 90%. In case of ETPPI it usually takes place through donation of electron from species with the loosely bounded electron such as p -electron in aromatic ring, or multiple bonds, or unpaired electrons in functional group that contain atom such as p to the vacant d-orbital of the transition metal (Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+}). The effective activation energies can be calculated at various concentration from the plot of $\log i_{\text{corr}}$ vs $1/T$ as shown in Table 3. The effective activation energies in the case of ETPPI are found to be higher than the E_{eff} of the corrosion process in 1 N sulfuric acid.

Table 3. Corrosion parameters of mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 in presence of ETPPI by thermodynamic studies

Temp. (K)	Conc. (mol L ⁻¹)	I_{con} (mA/cm ²)	$\log i_{\text{con}}$	I (%)	θ	$\theta/1-\theta$
298	10 ⁻³	0.22	-0.6575	95	0.95	19.0
	10 ⁻⁵	0.81	-0.0915	81	0.81	4.26
	10 ⁻⁷	1.3	0.1139	72	0.72	2.57
	H_2SO_4	4.6	0.6627	-	-	-
308	10 ⁻³	0.33	-0.4814	93	0.93	13.28
	10 ⁻⁵	1.2	0.0791	76	0.76	3.16
	10 ⁻⁷	1.5	0.1760	70	0.70	2.33
	H_2SO_4	5.1	0.7075	-	-	-
318	10 ⁻³	1.4	0.1461	84	0.84	5.25
	10 ⁻⁵	4.1	0.6127	55	0.55	1.22
	10 ⁻⁷	6.0	0.7781	33	0.33	0.42
	H_2SO_4	9.0	0.9542	-	-	-
328	10 ⁻³	3.5	0.5440	70	0.70	2.33
	10 ⁻⁵	5.2	0.71600	56	0.56	1.27
	10 ⁻⁷	7.0	0.8450	41	0.41	0.69
	H_2SO_4	12.0	1.0791	-	-	-

This conclusion shows that the ETPPI additive is very well adsorbed over the metal surface at lower temperatures and due to shortness of time lag between adsorption and desorption at 318 to 328 K, the relationship

becomes linear. This is also an indication that ETPPI belongs to first category of inhibitor as classified by Putilova. The two processes that mainly govern the adsorption behavior of ETPPI at a certain temperature are :

(i) The adsorption increases due to high charge density of the phosphorous atom.

(ii) The interaction between the ETPPI film through its partially delocalized π -electron with the vacant d-orbital of the metal surface.

Potentiostatic polarization :

A detailed study of the steady state potentiostatic polarization behavior of the anodic dissolution of mild steel in the presence and absence of various concentration of ETPPI has been done.

The effects of ETPPI have been interpreted in terms of the electrochemical parameters, e.g. critical current density (I_c), flade potential (E_{pp}) and passive current (i_p). The graph was plotted between logarithms of current density and potential. From the graph, the anodic dissolution parameters (i_c , E_{pp} , I_p) of mild steel in 1 N sulfuric acid solution at various concentration of the ETPPI can be calculated and they are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Electrochemical parameters for anodic dissolution of mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 in the presence of ETPPI

Solutions	Concentrations	$I_c \times 10^2$ (mA cm ⁻²)	I_p (mA cm ⁻²)	E_{pp} (mV) (Range)
H_2SO_4	1 N	2.81	1.25	475-1550
ETPPI	10 ⁻³	2.23	0.56	500-1495
	10 ⁻⁵	3.16	0.89	500-1535
	10 ⁻⁷	3.98	2.51	480-1490

The value of I_c is comparatively higher than the average passive current I_p . The I_c increase when concentration decreases. At higher concentration of inhibitors show low value of I_c , that is why ETPPI shows passivating behavior at all the concentrations. The synergistic effect is very much effective in the presence of I^- . The complex along with synergistic adsorption of I^- ions influence anodic dissolution of parameters of metals in the passive range.

The inhibitor shows strong delocalization of electrons and enhance overall electron density on the molecules. These are adsorbed much more strongly and uniformly. The ETPPI is able to form passive layer for all concen-

trations due to their better adsorption and less steric hindrance at higher concentration of $10^{-3} M$. ETPPI reduce I_c and I_p considerably and adsorb on the metal surface along with the already adsorbed anion (e.g. OH^- , Br^- , HSO_4^- and SO_4^{2-}). They form complex of the type $(M-I_n-A)_{ads}$, $(M-I_n)_{ads}$ or $(M-A-I_n)_{ads}$ thereby influencing the anodic dissolution parameters in the passive range. The passive film on mild steel is a combination of the above complex.

Infrared spectral studies :

Table 5 shows that on comparing the spectra of pure additive with that of adsorbed. It can be seen that many predominant peaks have either disappeared or shifted to

Table 5. Infrared bands for pure and adsorbed (on silica gel) ETPPI

Inhibitor	(C-H) bend. Ar. sub (cm^{-1})	(P-Ar) str. (cm^{-1})	(P-CH ₂) str. (cm^{-1})	(C-C) Ar str. (cm^{-1})
ETPPI	688.88, 739.42, 779.8	1482, 1163.04, 1112.34	1436.83	158.5
(ETPPI) _{ads}	689.10, 734.48, 796	-	1440	-

higher frequencies or appear with reduced intensities. Now it has been confirmed that adsorption of these additive is taking place on silica gel. The purpose of IR adsorption studies here is to show that these additive are adsorbed to a certain extent on silica gel. It is anticipated that this adsorption shall also be taken place on mild steel surface as well. Because it has Fe as a major constituent and the vacant d-orbital of Fe will be expected to have some interaction with the de-localized electrons associated with this additive.

Scanning electron microscopy :

Scanning electron microscopy of mild steel surface exposed to 1 N sulfuric acid in the presence of 10^{-3} and $10^{-7} M$ ETPPI concentrations respectively at magnification, from Fig. 1(c) and (d) shows almost 95% coverage of the metal surface by inhibitor molecule.

The overall result gives an idea that the ETPPI is a very effective inhibitor at 298 K and supplement the earlier results obtained from galvanostatic and potentiostatic techniques.

Fig. 1. SEM images of (A) mild steel, (B) mild steel in 1 N H₂SO₄, (C) $10^{-3} M$ ETPPI and (D) $10^{-7} M$ ETPPI.

Quantum chemical analysis :

The relation between inhibition characteristics and quantum chemical data shows that $\log I_{\text{cor}}$ mostly depends upon the energy of the HOMO and LUMO. In addition to the data, it can also be related to dipole moment charge on phosphorous and the shapes of the additive. The energy of HOMO is the theoretical analogue of the ionization potential of the additive whereas, the energy of LUMO represent electron affinity of the substance, that is why good donor and bad acceptor will be indicator of good inhibitor. Dipole charge value indicate that there is a possibility of donation of electron in the metal surface. In case of ETPPI, as shown in Fig. 2(a) and (b), do not make them a perfect donor of electron as is expected from quantum calculation and this may cause the cracks in protective covering layer. This is also the reason it is a good passivator at lower concentration and not at higher concentration. But the higher value of synergistic effect of I^- and less steric hindrance makes ETPPI a better inhibitor. From the HOMO and LUMO value it can be seen that additive could be an effective inhibitor because of synergetic effect of I^- with the help of Table 6.

Experimental

Preparation of ETPPI : All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

1.0 ml of triphenylphosphine was dissolved in minimum quantity of toluene and 1.2 mol of ethyl iodide was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 4–6 h, the solid was filtered and washed with excess toluene. The white crystals of ETPPI were obtained. The solid was crystallized from CHCl_3 /petroleum ether, characterized by standard techniques and melting point was recorded 442 K.

Mild steel grade IS-226 sample used for corrosion studies. The dimensions of specimen were $0.8 \times 0.8 \times 0.2$ cm. Each mild steel specimen were coated with epoxy resin (araldite) and then grinded so that a flat surface could be obtained for corrosion studies.

The electrochemical cell assembly of three electrode system was used for Tafel polarization and potentiodynamic polarization studies. Corrosion studies were conducted in 1 N H_2SO_4 in presence of difference concentration 10^{-3} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-7} M of ETPPI. A saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode, platinum as counter elec-

Fig. 2. Optimized geometry of ETPPI (A), space filled model (B), isosurface of total charge density (C), ball and stick model (D), electrostatic potential mapped onto 3-D isosurface of total charge density.

Table 6. Optimized AM1 parameters for ETPPI using hyperchem

Sl. No.	Inhibitors	ETPPI
1.	No. of electrons	105
2.	Total energy (kcal/mol)	-68458.3
3.	Energy of HOMO (eV)	-8.714476
4.	Energy of LUMO (eV)	-3.955748
5.	Binding energy kcal mol ⁻¹	-4347.041
6.	Isolated atomic energy kcal/mol	-64111.2634
7.	Electronic energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-526784.4
8.	Core-Core interaction (kcal mol ⁻¹)	458326.06621
9.	Heat of formation (kcal mol ⁻¹)	240.4711
10.	Dipoles (Debyes)	1.874 D
11.	Total charges on 'p'	-3.28293
12.	Molecular point group	C ₁
13.	Inhibition efficiency (%)	95

trode and mild steel as working electrode. The temperature of the cell was controlled by thermostatically using JULABO-40 circulating thermostat. Infrared spectroscopy was recorded in KBr medium, using Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectroscopy IR-37 for IR spectra. A saturated solution of the inhibitor was prepared in dry chloroform. The solution was added to a small quantity of silica gel and stirred vigorously. The solvent evaporated and the sample was dried. Small quantity of dry sample used for FTIR analysis. Surface analytical technique was performed on JEOL-840 scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Specimen were thoroughly washed in double distilled water and dried in a desiccator prior to SEM investigation.

Conclusion

From the overall data of adsorption of ETPPI on mild steel surface in acid solution was studied with the help of galvanostatic, temperature kinetics potentiostatic polarization studies, surface characterization, scanning electron microscopy, infrared studies and quantum chemical calculation. It can be concluded that :

- (i) ETPPI retard corrosion at ordinary temperature but enhance it at higher temperature. This shows that they belong to pitulovas 1st category of inhibitor.
- (ii) ETPPI are mixed inhibitor shows neither appreciable shift of E_{corr} towards any direction nor insignificant shift of OCP value (Open Current corrosion Potential).
- (iii) Irregular trends in Tafel slope values indicates that adsorption of the inhibiting species is as-

sisted by other ions present in the solution.

- (iv) Temkin's theory is adequate for explaining adsorption isotherm at all temperatures because it is multi layer adsorption.
- (v) Value of Q and E_{eff} indicate ETPPI is chemisorbed on the mild steel.
- (vi) Inhibition efficiency decrease with increase in temperature but it shows better inhibiting properties over wider range of temperature.
- (vii) From potentiodynamic studies it has been concluded that these inhibitor strongly adsorbed over metal surface and are good passivators in 1 N H₂SO₄. This passivation depends of already adsorbed anions of the medium.
- (viii) Quantum chemical calculation shows that ETPPI is a better inhibitor because of synergistic effect of Γ^- .

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